

**ENRICH
IN AFRICA**

D1.2 - Champions Application Form and Criteria

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Consortium:	IMPACT HUB – Austria EUROPEAN BUSINESS AND INNOVATION CENTRE NETWORK AISBL – Belgium SOCIEDADE PORTUGUESA DE INOVACO – Portugal AGORIZE SAS – France BONDY INNOVATION – France CO-CREATION HUB LIMITED – Nigeria I-HUB LIMITED – Kenya METHYS CONSULTING (PTY) LTD – South Africa TECH ACCELERATOR (PTY) LTD – South Africa SCIENCE, TECHNOLOGY AND INNOVATION POLICY RESEARCH ORGANISATION – Tanzania BPI FRANCE FINANCEMENT SA – France

About EiA: Funded by the European Union (Horizon 2020 programme), ENRICH in Africa is a project designed to bring together core stakeholders from both regions, in order to support and strengthen the European and African innovation ecosystem.

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D1.2 Champions Application Form and Criteria

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DISSEMINATION LEVEL

PU	Public	v
PP	Restricted to other program participants (including the EC services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the EC Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the EC)	

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DOCUMENT HISTORY

Revisions – Amendments

V1	Initial draft and content development
V2	Final version

Authors:

- Keva Richardson (Impact Hub GmbH)
- Faith Blakemore (Steinbeis 2i GmbH)

Reviewers:

- Dr Sandrine Doretto (Steinbeis 2i GmbH)

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Abbreviations

AEIP- Africa Europe Innovation Partnership

BPI- BPI France

EBN- European Business Network

EiA – ENRICH in Africa

GDPR- General Data Protection Regulation

IMPH- Impact Hub GmbH

M- Month

MOU- Memorandum of Understanding

PDF- Portable Document Format

S2i- Steinbeis 2i GmbH

UX- User Experience

WP- Work Package

1. Introduction

The ENRICH in Africa (EiA) Champion network is the core of the EiA project and provides on-the-ground support to African and European entrepreneurs. To ensure a solid foundation of business administration and development of the network, a Champion application form and associated criteria was developed. An overarching process and supporting document, within which to administer the applications was also developed, being designed to both facilitate the engagement of new Champions into the network as well as support the EiA partners to deliver the expected EiA expansion strategy, which foresees 40 new Champions onboarded by M12 and 100 by M36.

The first draft of the process was presented by the task leader to the task contributors in M4, with input received from the contributors then being integrated into later iterations. As a result, the following documents were produced and approved by EiA partners to support the process:

- **ENRICH in Africa Champions Application Process Document:** broken down into two sections, this document provides an overview of the application process (section 1) and the membership agreement text (section 2),
- **ENRICH in Africa Champions Application Form:** an external document for prospective incubators and accelerators to apply to the network and is the first part of the application and onboarding process,
- **ENRICH Champion Onboarding strategy:** ensures that applicants are processed effectively and efficiently but also acclimatises new champions into the network and engages them,
- **Champions Memorandum of Understanding (MOU):** The agreement between the Champions and EiA has been outlined in a formal document to provide clarity on role expectations from both sides. This is not a legally binding contract, but rather signals the willingness of the parties to move forward with a mutually beneficial relationship.

All documents have been designed following the EiA branding guidelines and with User Experience (UX) design theories in mind, e.g., providing 'return to top' icon at the bottom of the PDF pages, enabling the user to navigate the document as easily and simply as possible and thereby support document usage.

The outreach to new Champions using this documentation, followed a phased approach, reaching out to a range of pilot hubs first and foremost, whereby learnings about the form and usage could be gathered and further iterations developed before finalisation. These phases were:

1. Applications opened in June 2021 only to the Africa Europe Innovation Partnership (AEIP) network of hubs as part of the transition phase of this European Commission initiative as it moved towards closure in September 2021. In this phase, the Portable Document Format (PDF) application form was sent to AEIP partners for dissemination to their network with the understanding that all AEIP hubs were pre-approved to join EiA due to the criteria for AEIP closely matching that of EiA.
2. Applications opened in October 2021 to those potential Champions who had enquired about joining EiA and were placed on a waiting list.
3. Applications opened in November 2021 to the public and promoted through an ongoing communications campaign.

2. EiA Champion Application Process Document

2.1. Section 1- The Champion Application Process, Criteria and Benefits

To make the application process clear and understandable, section 1 of the document- EiA Champions Application Process Criteria and Benefits- has been shaped via a demand-side driven structure, building the knowledge of the reader in a step-by-step journey, which ensuring they receive the required information at the relevant moment to support their desire to apply. The overall section structure provides:

- **A visual graphic** of the overall process from beginning to end, providing context and enabling the readers to instantly understand the overall steps to achieve acceptance (Figure 1)
- **The criteria** upon which their application will be assessment- providing essential knowledge as to whether this process is relevant to the reader
- **Benefits listing**- the sales-based aspect of the document, ensuring that any reader reaching this stage then is motivated by the opportunity this network provides them.

Figure 1- Champions Application Process visual representation of steps

Following the visual introduction, potential applications are then provided with an understanding of the criteria on which their application will be assessed. This ensures that applicants who are not relevant to the network do not put in unnecessary efforts. These criteria, has also been indicated through the questions asked within the application form itself, creating further error prevention support for applicants.

The criteria for applications have been developed by the contributors of task 1.2, which is made up of pilot Champions, and therefore is created by the EiA network, for the EiA network. These criteria attain to ensure the process is as open as possible to the incubation and acceleration community of Europe and Africa, whilst also ensuring quality protections that protect as far as is reasonable, the brand of EiA.

These criteria states that the applications must:

- Provide incubation and/or acceleration programmes and services in Europe and/or Africa,
- Be an entity legally registered in a European or African country,
- Have been in operation for three years or more (where a name change of the company has occurred, total experience in the relevant services will be assessed),
- Agree with the terms and conditions of the membership agreement (provided beneath the process information within the same document),
- Agree to complete a self-assessment diagnostic when requested by EiA, for the purposes of understanding Champion needs and reflecting this in the service development and delivery.

In addition to these criteria, Champions are also informed that, should an existing Champion exist within the same city as the applicant, the existing Champion will be consulted to ascertain whether the inclusion of the new application would present any issues. In this way, existing relationships are shown to be valued and respected, further building the sense of engagement with EiA.

Once the criteria have been outlined, the reader is then provided with a clear and concise listing of the benefits of joining the Champions network. These benefits provide part of the sales-messaging for EiA, providing motivation to ensure as much as possible, that readers who have reached this stage of the document, understand why they should continue to complete the form.

The benefits listed, are:

- Full access to the EiA Champion Bootcamp,
- Full access to EiA Champions Academy (codified best practices for start-up support),
- EiA Mentoring programme,
- Optional twinning programme,
- Free EiA Annual congress ticket (guaranteed during life of EiA project),
- Hosting learning expeditions in collaboration with EiA,
- Online marketplace presence on the EiA digital platform,
- Access to the EiA community,
- Sales platform for services and self-generated reports,
- Co-generated commercialisation opportunities with EiA,
- Opportunity to be EiA subcontractor/implementation partner,
- Media opportunities,
- Network peer knowledge sharing opportunities,
- Soft landing partners for startups seeking internationalisation,
- Quality assurance label to support your sales approach.

2.2. Section 2- Membership Agreement

The membership agreement of the Champions Application Process provides general but essential information regarding the Champion network and relationship with EiA. This includes:

- **The purpose of EiA** (vision and mission)- providing context on the wider brand of EiA,
- **The role of a Champion**- what is expected from successful applicants,
- **The scope of the agreement**- to what extent this agreement impacts the relationship of the Champions and EiA,

- **A reiteration of the criteria alongside a description of the rights and obligations of Champions and EiA** within this relationship- providing more detailed information on the rights of both parties within the agreement and between the parties as individual entities,
- **Fee payments-** the expectations around any fees to be charged,
- **Terms and termination details-** providing clarity on exit procedures.

While not being required to be signed, this section of the document outlines the requirements within which an application moves forward should they wish to continue with an application. In this way, transparency is provided at the beginning of the process, building trust with applicants which is at the heart of EiA and essential for its success.

Again, the formulation of this agreement has been designed to be open and accepting of a wide range of potential Champions, ensuring that the reach of EiA can be as wide as necessary to fulfil its objectives to create a network of incubation and acceleration actors in both Europe and Africa. During the lifetime of the project, membership fees have been waived, ensuring that volume of Champions and the value of a multi-sided platform business model is achieved. Discussions will be held internally within the consortium and with the Champions under Work Package 5 and over the coming months, to determine the potential to be able to charge membership fees after the project end from 2024 onwards.

This entire document has been made available as a downloadable PDF sitting alongside the application form on the EiA project website, thus providing access to this information and process transparency for any potential applicants before they undertake any efforts (Figure 2).

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CHAMPION'S APPLICATION FORM

Do you deliver incubation or acceleration programmes in Europe or Africa?

Do you want to help your start-ups to internationalise?

Do you want the right tools and trainings to help strengthen your capacity?

If you have said yes to the above questions, then apply to become an ENRICH in Africa Champion!

(Please note you will be asked to upload a copy of your business registration document in this form, so make sure you have this to hand before you start...)

● Takes 7+ min

Let's start press Enter #

[Champions Application Process](#)

Figure 2- Champions application form and downloadable process document

The full EiA Champions Application Process document can also be found in Appendix 1- Champions Application Process Document.

3. EiA Champions Application Form

The EiA Champions Application Form has been developed via several iterations, taking the learnings from the piloted form and leading to the final version, which has been developed within the TypeForm platform and embedded in the EiA project website (Figure 2).

Initially developed as a PDF document, the Champions application form has been designed to ask relevant questions to understand the location and operational details of the application, ensure the criteria of the network membership is fulfilled and that the Champions can be aligned, via their service provision, to potential clients via the matching service provided through the Innovators Needs Assessment Form developed in WP2.

Following a similar style and UX design as the process document, the original application PDF ensured that the form was quick and easy to complete, thereby ensuring as high a completion rate as possible. This form was piloted through phase 1 applications with AEIP hubs, which attracted five applications. Of these five, three organisations were onboarded before the end of M12, with the other two onboarded by the end of February 2022. The delay in this onboarding was down to a lack of response from the application and delay in returning the MOU.

The PDF form followed a structure which led the applicant through a variety of increasingly individualised questions, thus deepening the understanding of the applicant. These sections are:

- **Your organisation**- broken down into sub sections regarding location within Africa or Europe,
- **Your services**- asking about service delivery type (incubator or accelerator), client groups, internationalisation support, services/programmes offered, experience, successes, and sector-focus,
- **Your network**- seeking information about key partners, team, networks, and their interest in EiA

Following the first and second phases of the application outreach, learnings were gathered regarding the usability of the form, including the viability of a PDF and its alignment to both the WP2 Needs Assessment Process and the website in general. Consultation with the task contributors led to the development of the TypeForm version of the application form, which provides the following additional benefits:

- **Digitalisation of the form**, allowing it to be embedded directly into the website and providing a smoother engagement process for potential applicants (Figure 1),
- **Automation and logic-based design** of the form reducing the content for applicants based on answers to questions (Figure 3),
- **Standardised** tools for the EiA brand, aligning with the WP2 TypeForm,
- **Capacity to easily compare and match** the results from the Champions Application Form and the Innovators Needs Assessment form, streamlining the EiA service provision.

Figure 3- Logic-based design of TypeForm application form

Additional learnings were also achieved through the consideration of this task alongside the work being planned for WP3, which sees the development of Champions services. The task collaborators saw the opportunity to add in questions to the TypeForm format, which explored with potential Champions their needs and goals for capacity development. By receiving this information at the beginning of the relationship with the Champion, not only can programmes be tailored better to the needs of the community, but the development of the Champions can be seen overtime and following the completion of programmes by EiA. For this reason, an additional set of questions were added to the form, and which explored Champions desired support requirement from EiA (Figure 4).

36 → We would now like to understand what areas of needs you have that EiA could support with.

Are there any areas of knowledge you would like to receive expert trainings on?

Description (optional)

Choose as many as you like

- A Specific industry sector in your region of interest
- B Specific technology fields
- C No, I don't need support in other areas of knowledge
- D Other

[Add choice](#)

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Figure 4- Needs assessment aspect of newly designed Champions Application Form

In addition, at the end of the form, a General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) opt-in question ensures that Champions agree to the storage and use of date for the purposes of delivering EiA activities (Figure 5).

40 → I understand and confirm my consent for ENRICH in Africa to store the contact details given here and survey information electronically and understand that this will be made accessible to ENRICH in Africa project partners only, in the interest of reviewing and confirming membership to the Champions programme. ENRICH in Africa project partners will comply with the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and not use any of the information provided except for the aforementioned purposes. I understand that my information will be stored until I request it to be deleted, which I can request at any time at hello@enrichin africa.com*

Description (optional)

- A Yes I accept

[Add choice](#)

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Figure 5- GDPR compliance within application form

A copy of the initial PDF version of the form can be found in Appendix 2- Original Champions Application Form PDF. The current TypeForm application can be found on the EiA website¹.

4. EiA Onboarding Strategy

While developing the application form, the task collaborators also discussed and developed an onboarding strategy, which provides the internal EiA team with a process within which to work to receive, assess and accept/decline new applications. This process provides an understanding of the triggers, actions, and processing steps for all applications (Figure 6). This process is broken down into two main phases- the pre-candidate review stage which provides due diligence to ensure the acceptance of relevant members to the network, and the onboarding stage. The first stage covers both options of the PDF form completion and the TypeForm completion, ensuring that the applicants receive the same support and documentation no matter how they apply.

	Pre-Candidate and Candidate Stage		Champion onboarding stage	
Trigger	Candidate Application completed	Candidate application reviewed	Champion accepted as a Candidate	Bootcamp
Action #1	Email sent to candidate to confirm receipt of application via typeform	Application filtered based on basic criteria: Legally registered in Europe or Africa 3+ years in operation (Include business registration certificate in application Or they an incubation or acceleration org	MOU sent to candidate for signing	Candidates attend next bootcamp
Action #2	Download application from Typeforms platform to shared drive	Check to see if there is an existing representative in the city the applicants operates in. Existing representative will be consulted, if no objections are received, applicant moves into candidate stage. If objections are raised, application will be flagged and will be considered by the committee, and a decision taken as to the ability to accept the new membership request.	Self-assessment diagnostic (from 3.1) with the welcome email are sent to Champion including link to the EuroQuity platform (intro to Anta) confirmation we will add them to the internal and external newsletters, explanation of services and contact details.	
Action #3	Candidate sent the terms and conditions of the membership agreement to be included in the website	Decline email sent to candidates who do not meet the basic criteria or where we have an existing champion.	Champion attends the next training on EiA, EuroQuity, and the Centre Platform	
Action #4		Notification email sent to candidates who move from pre-candidate stage to candidate stage.		
Action #5		Create non-verify pool for further investigation		

Figure 6- Champions selection process

Following agreement on this process, a database was created to contain the process data, onboarding process and the partners involved at each point. The data provided through completion of the form is then saved within both the TypeForm platform and the secure filing system provided by S2i as coordinators of the EiA project, which is delivered through Microsoft Teams. Information regarding data privacy and storage is provided and referred to on the EiA project website². Due to the confidential nature of this database, only the column header content provided within this spreadsheet can be provided within this report:

¹ <https://enrich-in-africa-project.eu/get-involved>

² <https://enrich-in-africa-project.eu/privacy-policy>

- **General Data:**
 - Date of Application
 - Company Name
 - Website address
 - Contact name
 - Email
 - City
 - Country
 - Incubator/accelerator
 - Startup or SME support provided?
- **Due Diligence Review-** to be completed by Impact Hub (IMPH)
 - Contacted to confirm acceptance of application (to be undertaken by Steinbeis 2i (S2i) as administrators of the champions@enrichinafrica.com email address)
 - Specific key partners identified
 - Existing for 3 years of more?
 - Legitimate website
 - Competing Champion existing?
 - Accept to next stage?
- **Champion acceptance/decline-** to be completed by S2i:
 - Contacted to accept- MOU sent?
 - Received MOU?
 - Declined Email sent?
- **Community onboarding:**
 - Attended onboarding to EuroQuity community? To be completed by BPI France (BPI)
 - Branding pack sent? To be completed by European Business Network (EBN)
- **Champion Engagement-** to be completed by IMPH:
 - Completed diagnostic?
 - Attended Bootcamp training?
 - Attended Champions Gathering?

Such a database enables team communication, data containment and progress of applications, which ensures a comprehensive and systematic integration of applicants into the process. Once the decision has been made, standardised email text has also been created to ensure that the acceptance or decline of applications can be delivered in an approved way. These standard texts are provided in Appendix 3- Standardised Acceptance and Decline Emails.

5. Champions Memorandum of Understanding

The final stage of the application process for successful applicants, is the MOU. This document provides the same information as detailed within section 2 of the Champions Application Form Process document, providing a succinct definition of the relationship between the Champion and EiA, with the successful Champions this time being asked to sign to accept the conditions. The MOU is sent to Champions as an attachment to the acceptance email and is required to be returned before the official onboarding of the Champion can be undertaken. At this point, however, the EiA team are activated to approach the Champion and provide them with the tools and information they need to feel informed and prepared to begin their membership with EiA.

A copy of the MOU is provided in Appendix 4- Champions Membership Agreement- Memorandum of Understanding.

6. Outcomes

As of M12, five applications were received from the AEIP via the PDF form, with three companies onboarded. A further twelve applications were also received, however, the onboarding for these were only achieved in January/February 2022. Since the beginning of 2022, a further four applications have been received by EiA, with four companies not meeting the criteria either due to not being incubators or accelerators, or due to the company being too young to meet the criteria. As of end of February, a total of seventeen new Champions have therefore been accepted and onboarded into the EiA network.

Analytics provided by TypeForm also demonstrates that there have been 681 views of the Champions Application form with 124 application forms being started. This provides a completion rate of 13.7% with the average time to completion being around 32 minutes. Such data demonstrates that this is further research to be undertaken to ascertain the reasons for the drop out rate, which it is foreseen will be undertaken by the new EiA Network Manager upon appointment, which is being undertaken as a part of WP5. Such foundational data, however, provides a strong starting point for the transition process between the EiA project, and the sustainable EiA Centre entity.

Appendix 1- Champions Application Process Document

ENRICH in Africa- Champions Application Process

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EiA Champion Application Process, Criteria and Benefits

1- Fill in the application form

- ↳ 2- The application will be reviewed by ENRICH in Africa (EiA) team
- ↳ 3- If your organization meets the criteria and there is no current EiA Champion in the city then membership will be confirmed!
- ↳ 4- If there is an existing representative in the city you operate in, the existing representative will be consulted, if no objections are received, your membership will be approved. If objections are raised, these will be considered by EiA, and a decision taken as to the ability to accept the new membership request. You will be notified of the outcome.
- ↳ 5- Accepted memberships are valid for one year and will be reviewed a month before the expiration date. NB- Membership runs from 1 January to 31 December each year.

Criteria:

To become a EiA Champion your organisation must:

- Be a Legal entity registered in Europe or an African country with more than three years of operations (where a name change of the company has occurred, total experience in the relevant services will be assessed).
- Have experience and track-record in providing incubation/acceleration for startups
- Agree with the terms and conditions of the membership agreement.
- Fill in a self-assessment diagnostic when requested by EiA.

Benefits:

- Full access to the EiA Champion Bootcamp,
- Full access to EiA Champions Academy (codified best practices for start-up support),
- EiA Mentoring programme,
- Optional twinning programme,
- Free EiA Annual congress ticket (guaranteed during life of EiA project),
- Hosting learning expeditions in collaboration with EiA,
- Online marketplace presence on the EiA digital platform,
- Access to the EiA community,
- Sales platform for services and self-generated reports,
- Co-generated commercialisation opportunities with EiA,
- Opportunity to be EiA subcontractor/implementation partner,
- Media opportunities,
- Network peer knowledge sharing opportunities,
- Soft landing partners for startups seeking internationalisation,
- Quality assurance label to support your sales approach.

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Membership Agreement

1. Preamble

Enrich in Africa (EiA) aims to engage with actors across the innovation ecosystem of Europe and Africa, bridging the space between politics and innovation actors.

EiA Vision

EiA believes in the potential of the innovation ecosystem across Europe and Africa to work successfully towards mutual benefits, and in the value that each region has to offer the other with regards to knowledge, technical innovation and creativity. EiA believes that in order to maximise this potential, conditions need to be provided, community needs to be nurtured and infrastructure needs to be built, that can offer value, sustainability and mutually beneficial co-creation.

EiA Mission

The mission of EiA activities is to connect European and African incubation and acceleration communities, in order to enhance innovation and co-creation opportunities. EiA will strive to reduce and/or overcome barriers to internationalisation for innovative SMEs and startups in Europe and Africa, empowering entrepreneurship and business success. This will be achieved through a designated set of services, delivered by a community-driven organisation (EiA Champions)

EiA Champions:

- An EiA member; an incubator/accelerator which becomes a member of the EiA network and identifies an individual staff member to act as the main contact point
- EiA Champions will have regional knowledge and a local focus, which means they understand the needs and opportunities for the local market, and are best placed to develop activities e.g., learning expeditions, alongside EiA, which can bring maximum local value. Also, able to connect into, or provide an overview of, the local triple helix-business, government, academia.
- EiA Champions might offer physical soft-landing services to support entrepreneurs who want to explore their local region with a view to selling into, finding partners within or setting up a business within the local market.
- EiA Champions can provide individualised services e.g., mentoring, training etc. to other Champions, including working closely with their twinned Champion to capacity build both areas.
- EiA Champions can generate reports and provide data to support the EiA provision of entrepreneurial trends, especially around tech transfer and internationalisation. Any sold reports/data provided by the Champions will generate a profit share for the Champion.

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- EIA Champions will co-develop and deliver the Learning Expeditions and share in the profit generated

2. Scope of the Membership Agreement

In this Agreement, the Parties wish to mutually establish their rights and obligations within the ENRICH in Africa Champions Network.

3. Criteria, Rights and Obligations:

3.1 EIA Champions criteria

EIA Champions must be able to demonstrate that they meet the following criteria:

- a) They work in a specific catchment area, geographical, sectorial or other. The scope of an EIA Champion can be local, regional, or can be widened to the national or international levels (e.g., responding to specific geographical and demographical territorial needs, for internationalization and soft-landing support services or for sectoral specialisation strategy). More than one EIA Champion can serve the same region, provided that they offer complementary services and serve the different sectors.
- b) Demonstrated knowledge and connections with the local start-up support ecosystem.
- c) They are a legal entity registered in Europe or Africa with more than three years of operations.
- d) They have experience and track record in providing incubation and acceleration programs and other services including but not limited to soft landing, workspace, mentoring, network events.
- e) They are committed to delivering start-up and incubation services with quality standards of the EIA Champion network
- f) They are committed to taking part in the capacity building activities provided by EIA, including but not limited to Bootcamp and online academy.
- g) They are committed to performing a self-assessment diagnostic
- h) They are committed to providing soft landing support for startups in their ecosystem.
- i) They are committed to working in partnership with other EIA Champions.

3.2 EIA Champion obligations

- a) Use EIA tech systems as and when required
- b) Promote the interests of the EIA Network and refrain from any activities that may harm the network, in particular not commit any offence or take any action which can undermine or devalue the reputation of the EIA network.
- c) Pay promptly and in full any fees as outlined in more detail in the Section below
- d) Ensure that the EIA Champion identifier is made properly visible on their website homepage. In addition to this, an EIA Champion must make visible the EIA logo on the premises of their organisation.

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- e) Ensure that their Champion profile is available and maintained on the EIA digital platform and EuroQuity Community pages.
- f) Provide a representative to attend the Annual Champions Gathering event, to be held once a year.
- g) Accept to receive the EIA internal newsletter and relevant communications from EIA

3.3 EIA Champions shall be entitled to exercise the following rights, subject to fulfilment of its membership obligations

- Be an EIA representative in a specific city, regional or country.
- Participate fully in the training and other capacity upgrading and networking activities provided by the EIA Center
- Be a preferable partner of the EIA Centre in business and programmatic opportunities.

3.4 Responsibilities and Obligations of the EIA Center

- Provide branding elements to ensure Champions can meet their obligations as described in section 3.2-d above
- Process applications in a fair and justifiable manner
- Provide a community hub and online platform to enable Champions to connect to peers and promote their services
- Provide a 50% profit share of any sales made from activities jointly undertaken by Champions and EIA e.g., Learning Expedition fees and publication sales. Such activities and profit share must be confirmed in advance of any sales
- Provide relevant services to support the Champions in upgrading their capacity to deliver quality services to innovators and entrepreneurs
- Provide relevant opportunities to engage with the wider innovation ecosystem across Europe and Africa
- Provide a contact point within EIA to support with networking and Champion engagement
- Provide relevant channels for regular communication of EIA activities and developments

4. Fee Payments

4.1 Fee Waiver

While EIA functions as a European Project, all fees for membership and/or services will be waived. This status will remain in force and up until the end of December 2023.

During this time and as part of the piloting process of the project, assessments will be made with regard to the sustainability of the EIA business model and the requirement and amount of fees will be considered. Such considerations will be conducted via an internal consortium review and in negotiation with current Champions. All final decisions and outcomes will be communicated to the Champions before the end of December 2023.

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5. Terms and Termination

5.1 Agreement Affective Date

The Agreement shall become effective as of the date of application form acceptance by EIA and shall be in force for the life of the Champion membership.

5.2 Agreement Prolongation

At the end of the first year within which the application has been made, the Agreement shall be automatically prolonged unless terminated by either Party with written notice one month prior to the expiry of any such term.

5.2 Agreement Termination

At any time during the term of the Agreement, all Parties shall be entitled to terminate the Agreement. Upon termination, the EIA Champion shall immediately cease to use EIA branding, network benefits and use of EIA systems.

Without limitation to any of the above, EIA shall be entitled to terminate this agreement with immediate effect, under certain circumstances pertaining to EIA including but not limited to: material breach of this Agreement; insolvency; unauthorized assignment, transfer or subcontracting of rights under this Agreement, endangering the reputation of the ENRICH in Africa network or branding in any material way.

Appendix 2- Original Champions Application Form PDF

EiA Champion Application Form

Your Organisation																																																											
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City:																																																											
Post code:																																																											
Country:	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th colspan="2">Africa</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Algeria</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Liberia</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Angola</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Libya</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Benin</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Madagascar</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Botswana</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Malawi</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Burkina Faso</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Mali</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Burundi</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Mauritania</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Cabo Verde</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Mauritius</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Cameroon</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Morocco</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Central African Republic (CAR)</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Mozambique</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Chad</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Namibia</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Comoros</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Niger</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Congo, Democratic Republic of the</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Nigeria</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Congo, Republic of the</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Rwanda</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Cote d'Ivoire</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Sao Tome and Principe</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Djibouti</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Senegal</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Egypt</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Seychelles</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Equatorial Guinea</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Sierra Leone</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Eritrea</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Somalia</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Cabo Verde</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> South Africa</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Eswatini</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> South Sudan</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Ethiopia</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Sudan</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Gabon</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Tanzania</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Gambia</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Togo</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Ghana</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Tunisia</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Guinea</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Uganda</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Guinea-Bissau</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Zambia</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Kenya</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Zimbabwe</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Lesotho</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Africa		<input type="checkbox"/> Algeria	<input type="checkbox"/> Liberia	<input type="checkbox"/> Angola	<input type="checkbox"/> Libya	<input type="checkbox"/> Benin	<input type="checkbox"/> Madagascar	<input type="checkbox"/> Botswana	<input type="checkbox"/> Malawi	<input type="checkbox"/> Burkina Faso	<input type="checkbox"/> Mali	<input type="checkbox"/> Burundi	<input type="checkbox"/> Mauritania	<input type="checkbox"/> Cabo Verde	<input type="checkbox"/> Mauritius	<input type="checkbox"/> Cameroon	<input type="checkbox"/> Morocco	<input type="checkbox"/> Central African Republic (CAR)	<input type="checkbox"/> Mozambique	<input type="checkbox"/> Chad	<input type="checkbox"/> Namibia	<input type="checkbox"/> Comoros	<input type="checkbox"/> Niger	<input type="checkbox"/> Congo, Democratic Republic of the	<input type="checkbox"/> Nigeria	<input type="checkbox"/> Congo, Republic of the	<input type="checkbox"/> Rwanda	<input type="checkbox"/> Cote d'Ivoire	<input type="checkbox"/> Sao Tome and Principe	<input type="checkbox"/> Djibouti	<input type="checkbox"/> Senegal	<input type="checkbox"/> Egypt	<input type="checkbox"/> Seychelles	<input type="checkbox"/> Equatorial Guinea	<input type="checkbox"/> Sierra Leone	<input type="checkbox"/> Eritrea	<input type="checkbox"/> Somalia	<input type="checkbox"/> Cabo Verde	<input type="checkbox"/> South Africa	<input type="checkbox"/> Eswatini	<input type="checkbox"/> South Sudan	<input type="checkbox"/> Ethiopia	<input type="checkbox"/> Sudan	<input type="checkbox"/> Gabon	<input type="checkbox"/> Tanzania	<input type="checkbox"/> Gambia	<input type="checkbox"/> Togo	<input type="checkbox"/> Ghana	<input type="checkbox"/> Tunisia	<input type="checkbox"/> Guinea	<input type="checkbox"/> Uganda	<input type="checkbox"/> Guinea-Bissau	<input type="checkbox"/> Zambia	<input type="checkbox"/> Kenya	<input type="checkbox"/> Zimbabwe	<input type="checkbox"/> Lesotho	
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1

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Europe	
<input type="checkbox"/> Albania <input type="checkbox"/> Andorra <input type="checkbox"/> Armenia <input type="checkbox"/> Austria <input type="checkbox"/> Azerbaijan <input type="checkbox"/> Belarus <input type="checkbox"/> Belgium <input type="checkbox"/> Bosnia and Herzegovina <input type="checkbox"/> Bulgaria <input type="checkbox"/> Croatia <input type="checkbox"/> Cyprus <input type="checkbox"/> Czechia <input type="checkbox"/> Denmark <input type="checkbox"/> Estonia <input type="checkbox"/> Finland <input type="checkbox"/> France <input type="checkbox"/> Georgia <input type="checkbox"/> Germany <input type="checkbox"/> Greece <input type="checkbox"/> Hungary <input type="checkbox"/> Iceland <input type="checkbox"/> Ireland <input type="checkbox"/> Italy <input type="checkbox"/> Kazakhstan <input type="checkbox"/> Kosovo	<input type="checkbox"/> Latvia <input type="checkbox"/> Liechtenstein <input type="checkbox"/> Lithuania <input type="checkbox"/> Luxembourg <input type="checkbox"/> Malta <input type="checkbox"/> Moldova <input type="checkbox"/> Monaco <input type="checkbox"/> Montenegro <input type="checkbox"/> Netherlands <input type="checkbox"/> North Macedonia <input type="checkbox"/> Norway <input type="checkbox"/> Poland <input type="checkbox"/> Portugal <input type="checkbox"/> Romania <input type="checkbox"/> Russia <input type="checkbox"/> San Marino <input type="checkbox"/> Serbia <input type="checkbox"/> Slovakia <input type="checkbox"/> Slovenia <input type="checkbox"/> Spain <input type="checkbox"/> Sweden <input type="checkbox"/> Switzerland <input type="checkbox"/> Turkey <input type="checkbox"/> Ukraine <input type="checkbox"/> United Kingdom
Website URL:	
Name of contact/ representative for EIA network:	
Email Address of your representative:	
Please confirm your organization is legally registered in Europe or Africa:	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (If no, please be aware that we will not be able to accept your application at this time)

2

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If yes, what year was your entity registered?	
Please provide the company registration number:	
Please provide the city/country of registration:	
Has your entity existed under a previous name in the past 3 years'?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
If yes, please provide the name and registration number for the previous company, as well as a brief description of the business:	
Your Services	
Please select your main service type:	<input type="checkbox"/> Incubator <input type="checkbox"/> Accelerator <input type="checkbox"/> Both of the above
Who are your main customers?	<input type="checkbox"/> Startups <input type="checkbox"/> SMEs (Small and Medium Enterprises) <input type="checkbox"/> Both
Are you able to support international companies looking to enter your local market?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
Please select which funds and/or areas of advice you already offer to companies:	<u>Financing and Funding:</u> <input type="checkbox"/> Seed funding <input type="checkbox"/> Venture capital <input type="checkbox"/> Corporate financing <input type="checkbox"/> Public grant applications <input type="checkbox"/> Crowdfunding <input type="checkbox"/> Credit/loan advice

3

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	<p><u>Business Support:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Co-working space <input type="checkbox"/> Office space <input type="checkbox"/> Access to local talent <input type="checkbox"/> Access to local partners <input type="checkbox"/> Access to local researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Access to ancillary services e.g., legal, financial and tax/ accounting <input type="checkbox"/> Tech transfer support <input type="checkbox"/> Innovation Management consultation <p><u>Internationalisation Support:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Local Ecosystem reports <input type="checkbox"/> Soft-landing programmes <input type="checkbox"/> Inbound trade missions <input type="checkbox"/> Outbound trade missions <input type="checkbox"/> Visa advice/guidance/support <input type="checkbox"/> Localisation advice/guidance/support e.g., schools, doctors etc. <p><u>Training Services:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Teambuilding and culture <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management <input type="checkbox"/> Business model design and development <input type="checkbox"/> Financial planning <input type="checkbox"/> Marketing, sales and growth hacking <input type="checkbox"/> Investment pitching, funding and Investor relations <input type="checkbox"/> Industry specific training (Please state in which sectors) <input type="checkbox"/> Technology specific trainings (Please state in which technologies)
<p>Please describe any additional services you provide to companies:</p>	

4

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<p>Please describe your experience in providing support for startups and/or SMEs (please add any relevant links to examples of programmes and/ or annual reports where relevant):</p>	
<p>How many businesses have you successfully Incubated/Accelerated (since your opening)?</p>	
<p>List the past projects your organization has implemented (provide links please where applicable):</p>	
<p>What sectors are your programmes focused on?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Energy & Renewables <input type="checkbox"/> Materials and resources <input type="checkbox"/> Manufacturing and automation <input type="checkbox"/> Mobility and transportation <input type="checkbox"/> ICT and telecoms <input type="checkbox"/> Retails and e-commerce <input type="checkbox"/> Construction and real estate <input type="checkbox"/> Finance and insurance <input type="checkbox"/> Food and agriculture <input type="checkbox"/> Fashion, sport and leisure <input type="checkbox"/> Healthcare and life sciences <input type="checkbox"/> Culture, education and media <input type="checkbox"/> Business and professional services

5

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Your Network	
Who are the key partners you work with?	<input type="checkbox"/> Early- stage investors <input type="checkbox"/> Venture capital investors <input type="checkbox"/> Corporates <input type="checkbox"/> Public Authority <input type="checkbox"/> Banks <input type="checkbox"/> Innovation consultants <input type="checkbox"/> Researchers/universities <input type="checkbox"/> Other: (please state)
Please name here some of your specific key partners you are able to share with us:	
What is the size of your team? Where possible, please add LinkedIn profiles of your leadership team as supporting information:	
Please provide us with the names of any networks or professional bodies you are members of:	
We would like to hear from you why you are interested in becoming a part of the EIA Network and what you hope to gain from being a Champion?	

Signature

I, as the official representative of the above-named organisation, confirm the information provided in this application, is a true and accurate representation of our company and activities, and accept the conditions of the membership application agreement.

Signature: _____

Name: _____

Date: _____

Location: _____

Once complete, please return to champions@enrichinafrica.com

Thanks!

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Appendix 3- Standardised Acceptance and Decline Emails

Acceptance Email Text

Dear ,

Thank you for your patience. We have now finalised the initial review process of your application to become an ENRICH in Africa Champion, and I am pleased to be able to **now officially accept your application and welcome you into our community!** To confirm this process, I am sending you here our MOU, which describes what you can expect from us and what being a Champion will entail. **Please sign and return this to us as soon as you are able** (a digital signature is also acceptable). We would like to now add you to our website- to do this, can you please send us, along with your MOU, **a copy of your logo?**

It is wonderful to be able to add you to our growing network of incubators and accelerators across Europe and Africa, for whom we are developing a wide range of services. The timing of your application is particularly good, in that we will be opening the services for our Champions in early 2022. This will include **twinning opportunities with peers in Africa, a mentoring programme, virtual academy, bootcamp training and access to our brand-new platform to help promote your services to relevant start-ups who can benefit from your expertise.**

For now, my colleagues [@Covadonga Rayon](#) and [@Dawit Dagne](#) will add you to our **internal newsletter** where you will receive information on a bi-monthly basis about the development of the network and upcoming opportunities, as well as our **external newsletter** (also bi-monthly) which is our communication channel with our wider stakeholders. We would also like to get you bolted into **our community**- for this I am cc'ing in my colleague [@Anta DIALLO](#) who manages the community on the [EuroQuity platform](#). This platform helps you and your cohorts to connect to peers, potential partners and investors. Anta will be able to explain the process and help onboard you to the platform, as well as introduce you to the **ENRICH in Africa Champions label** and how you can use this to generate value and benefits as a member of our network.

As soon as I receive your signed MOU, I will be able to send you the **branding pack**, which will provide you with the items you will need to promote your participation in our network. We will then also add you to our **pool of Champions** as we receive enquiries from start-ups and seek to connect them to appropriate potential service providers. For this, we will simply use the information you have provided to us in your application form so there is nothing else for you to do here. My colleague [@Xia Wei La](#) is overseeing this process so will be in touch with you if required.

If you have any questions or would like to discuss anything about ENRICH in Africa in the meantime, please don't hesitate to contact either myself or my colleague [@Keva Richardson](#). We are all here to support you and look forward to engaging with you in the future!

Best regards

Decline Email Text- Not an incubator/accelerator

Dear ,

Thank you for your application to join the ENRICH in Africa network as a Champion. As per our criteria, we have created the Champions network specifically for companies offering incubation and acceleration activities across Europe and Africa. We have reviewed your application and it appears that your organisation is outside of this definition and therefore, we must unfortunately decline your application.

There are, however, other ways to engage with the ENRICH in Africa activities. Our online community is open for all innovation stakeholders across the continents, providing information, networking, and events. If you haven't already, please check out our community in the EuroQuity platform [here](#).

You can also sign up for our newsletter and keep in touch, with all the activities we will be offering for entrepreneurs and facilitators alike. Some of our upcoming activities will include scale-up, start-up and soft-landing programmes, as well as our annual EiA Congress, which will draw together organisations such as yours alongside other innovation actors to engage in discussion and learnings aiming to move innovation forward for both regions.

Our new platform will also be launched soon, offering companies such as yours a place to find and promote a wide range of various activities. We will be promoting the launch of this online hub through our social media, newsletter and community channels, so make sure to follow us online to hear first about this and all our other news.

We look forward to engaging with you in other ways and thank you again for your interest in ENRICH in Africa.

Best Regards,

Decline Email Text- Company under 3-years old

Dear ,

Thank your for completing the application form to become an EiA Champion.

In order to ensure a strong and valuable network, we have placed certain, essential criteria upon acceptance of applications, one of which is that companies need to have been in existence for 3 years or more. From your application, I can see that your company has only been in existence since last March, and therefore we are unable, at this point, to accept your application.

There are, however, other ways to engage with the ENRICH in Africa activities. Our online community is open for all innovation stakeholders across the continents, providing information, networking, and events. If you haven't already, please check out our community in the EuroQuity platform [here](#).

You can also sign up for our newsletter and keep in touch, with all the activities we will be offering for entrepreneurs and facilitators alike. Some of our upcoming activities will include scale-up, start-up and soft-landing programmes, as well as our annual EiA Congress, which will draw together organisations

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We look forward to engaging with you in other ways and thank you again for your interest in ENRICH in Africa.

Best Regards,

Appendix 4- Champions Membership Agreement- Memorandum of Understanding

ENRICH in Africa- Champions Membership Agreement- Memorandum of Understanding

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Membership Agreement.....	2
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2. Scope of the Membership Agreement.....	3
3. Criteria, Rights and Obligations:.....	3
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5. Terms and Termination	5
Signature	5

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Membership Agreement

1. Preamble

Enrich in Africa (EiA) aims to engage with actors across the innovation ecosystem of Europe and Africa, bridging the space between politics and innovation actors.

EiA Vision

EiA believes in the potential of the innovation ecosystem across Europe and Africa to work successfully towards mutual benefits, and in the value that each region has to offer the other with regards to knowledge, technical innovation and creativity. EiA believes that in order to maximise this potential, conditions need to be provided, community needs to be nurtured and infrastructure needs to be built, that can offer value, sustainability and mutually beneficial co-creation.

EiA Mission

The mission of EiA activities is to connect European and African incubation and acceleration communities, in order to enhance innovation and co-creation opportunities. EiA will strive to reduce and/or overcome barriers to internationalisation for innovative SMEs and startups in Europe and Africa, empowering entrepreneurship and business success. This will be achieved through a designated set of services, delivered by a community-driven organisation (EiA Champions)

EiA Champions:

- An EiA member; an incubator/accelerator which becomes a member of the EiA network and identifies an individual staff member to act as the main contact point
- EiA Champions will have regional knowledge and a local focus, which means they understand the needs and opportunities for the local market, and are best placed to develop activities e.g., learning expeditions, alongside EiA, which can bring maximum local value. Also, able to connect into, or provide an overview of, the local triple helix-business, government, academia.
- EiA Champions might offer physical soft-landing services to support entrepreneurs who want to explore their local region with a view to selling into, finding partners within or setting up a business within the local market.
- EiA Champions can provide individualised services e.g., mentoring, training etc. to other Champions, including working closely with their twinned Champion to capacity build both areas.
- EiA Champions can generate reports and provide data to support the EiA provision of entrepreneurial trends, especially around tech transfer and internationalisation. Any sold reports/data provided by the Champions will generate a profit share for the Champion.

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- EIA Champions will co-develop and deliver the Learning Expeditions and share in the profit generated

2. Scope of the Membership Agreement

In this Agreement, the Parties wish to mutually establish their rights and obligations within the ENRICH in Africa Champions Network.

3. Criteria, Rights and Obligations:

3.1 EIA Champions criteria

EiA Champions must be able to demonstrate that they meet the following criteria:

- They work in a specific catchment area, geographical, ~~sectorial~~ or other. The scope of an EiA Champion can be local, regional, or can be widened to the national or international levels (e.g., responding to specific geographical and demographical territorial needs, for internationalization and soft-landing support services or for sectoral specialisation strategy). More than one EiA Champion can serve the same region, ~~provided that~~ they offer complementary services and serve the different sectors.
- Demonstrated knowledge and connections with the local start-up support ecosystem.
- They are a legal entity registered in Europe or Africa with more than three years of operations.
- They have experience and track record in providing incubation and acceleration programs and other services including but not limited to soft landing, workspace, mentoring, network events.
- They are committed to delivering start-up and incubation services with quality standards of the EiA Champion network
- They are committed to taking part in the capacity building activities provided by EiA, including but not limited to Bootcamp and online academy.
- They are committed to performing a self-assessment diagnostic
- They are committed to providing soft landing support for startups in their ecosystem.
- They are committed to working in partnership with other EiA Champions.

3.2 EiA Champion obligations

- Use EiA tech systems as and when required
- Promote the interests of the EiA Network and refrain from any activities that may harm the network, ~~in particular not~~ commit any offence or take any action which can undermine or devalue the reputation of the EiA network.
- Pay promptly and in full any fees as outlined in more detail in the Section below
- Ensure that the EiA Champion identifier is made properly visible on their website homepage. In addition to this, an EiA Champion must make visible the EiA logo on the premises of their organisation.

3

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- e) Ensure that their Champion profile is available and maintained on the EIA digital platform and EuroQuity Community pages.
- f) Provide a representative to attend the Annual Champions Gathering event, to be held once a year.
- g) Accept to receive the EIA internal newsletter and relevant communications from EIA

3.3 EIA Champions shall be entitled to exercise the following rights, subject to fulfilment of its membership obligations

- Be an EIA representative in a specific city, regional or country.
- Participate fully in the training and other capacity upgrading and networking activities provided by the EIA Center
- Be a preferable partner of the EIA Centre in business and programmatic opportunities.

3.4 Responsibilities and Obligations of the EIA Center

- Provide branding elements to ensure Champions can meet their obligations as described in section 3.2-d above
- Process applications in a fair and justifiable manner
- Provide a community hub and online platform to enable Champions to connect to peers and promote their services
- Provide a 50% profit share of any sales made from activities jointly undertaken by Champions and EIA e.g., Learning Expedition fees and publication sales. Such activities and profit share must be confirmed in advance of any sales
- Provide relevant services to support the Champions in upgrading their capacity to deliver quality services to innovators and entrepreneurs
- Provide relevant opportunities to engage with the wider innovation ecosystem across Europe and Africa
- Provide a contact point within EIA to support with networking and Champion engagement
- Provide relevant channels for regular communication of EIA activities and developments

4. Fee Payments

4.1 Fee Waiver

While EIA functions as a European Project, all fees for membership and/or services will be waived. This status will remain in force and up until the end of December 2023.

During this time and as part of the piloting process of the project, assessments will be made with regard to the sustainability of the EIA business model and the requirement and amount of fees will be considered. Such considerations will be conducted via an internal consortium review and in negotiation with current Champions. All final decisions and outcomes will be communicated to the Champions before the end of December 2023.

4

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5. Terms and Termination

5.1 Agreement Affective Date

The Agreement shall become effective as of the date of application form acceptance by EiA and shall be in force for the life of the Champion membership.

5.2 Agreement Prolongation

At the end of the first year within which the application has been made, the Agreement shall be automatically prolonged unless terminated by either Party with written notice one month prior to the expiry of any such term.

5.2 Agreement Termination

At any time during the term of the Agreement, all Parties shall be entitled to terminate the Agreement. Upon termination, the EiA Champion shall immediately cease to use EiA branding, network benefits and use of EiA systems.

Without limitation to any of the above, EiA shall be entitled to terminate this agreement with immediate effect, under certain circumstances pertaining to EiA including but not limited to: material breach of this Agreement; insolvency; unauthorized assignment, transfer or subcontracting of rights under this Agreement, endangering the reputation of the ENRICH in Africa network or branding in any material way.

Signature

I, the undersigned, acting on behalf of the applying company, agree to the above membership agreement as a memorandum of understanding with ENRICH in Africa, who have drafted and also agree to these terms.

Name:

Position:

Email:

Applying Company Name:

Date:

Location: (City/Country)

Signature:

5

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